

Factors affecting the decision to choose a university of high school students: A study in An Giang Province, Vietnam

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ABSTRACT

It is important to provide high school students with the necessary information for them to consult and make a decision to choose a university. The study aims to identify and evaluate the influence of factors in the decision to choose a university for high school students. The questionnaire survey method was used to collect data from 393 students from eight high schools in An Giang Province, Vietnam. Exploratory factor analysis and linear regression were used to analyze the data. The research results show that students are quite satisfied and quite certain with their decision to choose a university, while there are six important factors affecting the decision to choose a university. Influential factors with decreasing order of magnitude are: i) Factors consulted by teachers, family, friends, and relatives; ii) Factors of future job opportunities; iii) Factors of media activities; iv) Factors of learning conditions; v) Factors of university reputation; vi) Factors belong to the students themselves. The findings of the study show that there is no statistically significant difference between the group of males and females, between grades 10, 11, and 12. Besides, there is a statistically significant difference between students in high schools. The findings of this study have theoretical and practical implications for university admissions in Vietnam. Proposals made to university administrators were discussed. From the research results, we want to help students find the right university, and support universities to improve the efficiency of admissions.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Currently, the requirement for highly qualified human resources plays a decisive role in the socio-economic development of each country. The job issue is fiercely competitive, so it requires the quality of graduates to meet the requirements of society [1]. This brings many opportunities as well as challenges for employees [2]. Therefore, university students should perfect their skills and improve their knowledge to create a competitive advantage in the labor market. In addition, students attending a quality university is also an important factor in increasing their chances of getting a job [3]. Therefore, high school students, especially 12th graders, are very interested in choosing majors, and universities. It suits their interests, and there are many opportunities to find a job after graduation [4].

According to the general statistics office in 2019, there are 237 universities in Vietnam, and in 2020 there are 2,653,995 high school students in the whole country [5]. Every year, a large number of students take the entrance exam to universities. However, difficult admission to universities is a common situation in most Vietnamese universities today. This has shown that students' tendency to choose universities has changed, which leads to many universities not recruiting enough. What should we do to make high school students realize the importance of choosing the right university and studying the right major, it will help them get good jobs in the future [6]. Because nowadays many students after graduation have to work outside the field they studied or have to be retrained from scratch, it is one of the existing problems [7].

Many high school students aspire to study in universities, even though they are students with average academic ability [8]. In addition, many students have chosen a major that is not suitable for their ability, because they are influenced by family, and friends, or choose a major or university according to crowd psychology [9]. It leads to many students making wrong decisions. Therefore, choosing a major and university is very important, as it is one of the factors that determine a person's future.

Education and training in Vietnam are taking place according to the trend of socialization. Many new universities appear to create competition between universities, they want to attract a large number of students to apply to university. One of the factors determining the current competitiveness of universities is the quality of training and the percentage of students who have stable jobs [10]. Universities should regularly conduct surveys to get students' opinions in order to understand the important factors that influence the decision-making process of choosing a university [11]. Thereby satisfying the requirements and receiving satisfaction from the students, creates the motivation to attract more students to the university.

There have been many studies showing the concern of students about the cost of study, facilities, environment, and the reputation of the university; counseling of reference groups for students; learner point of view. It has a direct impact on the intention to choose a university for high school students [12]. The reputation of the university was identified as a factor that positively influenced students' decision to choose a university. Therefore, improving the university's reputation should also be identified as a solution to better attract new students to universities [13].

Training programs at universities should be regularly updated and perfected. The training program needs to be adjusted to match the training objectives of universities and the needs of employers, students, and related units [14]. With the expectation of wanting to acquire knowledge and skills when studying at university, students are interested in learning programs with many practical contents to meet the needs of employers [15]. In the context of industrial revolution 4.0, training programs also need to be built in an open direction. Accordingly, learners can also access E-learning to interact, and share documents for students to access, and exchange easily.

Universities should pay more attention to building a system that provides information about the school so that students can easily search and refer to it. Upgrade the website system with a lot of useful information, an easy-to-follow interface, and look-up information [16]. Besides, social networks are also a channel of information to quickly and closely reach high school students [17]. Universities can increase interaction with prospective students through their official Fan pages [18].

The objective of the study is to identify and evaluate the factors affecting the decision to choose a university for high school students in Vietnam. It is necessary for the current period. Based on the research results, we discuss and suggest some solutions to help students find the right university for themselves, and support universities to improve the effectiveness of recruitment in the future.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Research sample

To be able to determine the factors affecting the decision to choose a university for high school students. The study examined research theories and used focus groups to discuss with students and teachers in high schools in An Giang province; students and lecturers of An Giang University, Vietnam. During the focus group discussions, the participants were provided with a list of factors that led to the decision to choose a university; and they were asked to give their opinions on the factors that influence high school student's decision to choose a university; the addition of the missing elements to the list. The consensus reached at the end of this period allowed six factors (to 31 observed variables, respectively) to be identified.

Based on these preliminary results, a questionnaire was developed to gain insight into the factors influencing the high school student's decision to choose a university. The survey included 40 Likert items. Demographic questions sought information on gender, grade, high school, and six factors influencing high school student's decision to choose a university. Likert scale is used with values from 1 to 5 to measure the perceived level of survey respondents 1 (Strongly disagree), 2 (Disagree), 3 (Neutral), 4 (Agree), 5 (Strongly agree) to show how important it is.

An Giang province in the southwestern region of Vietnam. According to 2017 statistics, An Giang province has a population of 2,161,700 people; the number of high school students is 46,222; the rate of students graduating from high school is 99.53% [5]. The questionnaire survey method was used. A total of 393 students were surveyed. The eight surveyed high schools in An Giang province include: Thoai Ngoc Hau High School; Long Xuyen High School; Thu Khoa Nghia High School; Nguyen Huu Canh High School; Nguyen Binh Khiem High School; Nguyen Trung Truc High School; Chu Van A High School; Nguyen Khuyen High School as presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Description of the sample surveyed

Research factor	Number of people	Percentage
1. Gender	393	100%
Male	188	47.8
Female	205	52.2
2. Grade	393	100%
Grade 10	95	24.2
Grade 11	106	27.0
Grade 12	192	48.9
3. High Schools	393	100%
High School Thoai Ngoc Hau	27	6.9
High School Long Xuyen	54	13.7
High School Thu Khoa Nghia	35	8.9
High School Nguyen Huu Canh	70	17.8
High School Nguyen Binh Khiem	32	8.1
High School Nguyen Khuyen	82	20.9
High School Chu Van An	33	8.4
High School Nguyen Trung Truc	60	15.3

2.2. Research instruments

Research on the decision to choose a university for high school students has had several studies done. Chapman has researched on student university choice model. The study proposed a model with five elements including efforts to communicate with students; cost; important people; abilities; and passion level of the student [19]. The interesting point is that he noticed the characteristics of the student's family and individual (also known as the group of internal factors); characteristics of the university and the university's communication efforts (known as the group of external factors) are two groups of factors that greatly influence students' decision to choose a university.

Hossler and Gallagher once again affirmed that in addition to the strong influence of family, the influence of friends is also one of the strong influences on students' decision to choose a university [9]. Besides, classmates at the same school and teachers have a significant influence on students' decisions to choose a university. The research model of Kallio also shows that gender also has an impact on the decision to choose a university. The level of impact of groups of factors will be significantly influenced by the gender characteristics of students [20]. He believes that different genders will have different degrees of indirect impact on students' decision to choose a university. Cabrera and La Nasa studied a three-stage model of students' college choice. Which, the student's future job expectations are very important in influencing the student's decision to choose a university [21]. Thus, many different factors can influence a student's decision to choose a university. The tested theoretical models will be the basis for forming the experimental model in this study [22].

Based on the research theoretical framework and research model of previous researchers [9], [19], [21], [23], the researchers proposed research model factors affecting decisions in choosing a university for high school students has six independent variables including: i) Factors advised by teachers, family, friends, relatives; ii) Factors belonging to the student himself; iii) Factors of learning conditions; iv) Factor of university reputation; v) Factors of media activities; vi) Factor of future job opportunities as displayed in Figure 1. The six factors included in the model are relevant to the context of higher education in Vietnam: Factors consulted by teachers, family, friends, and relatives (COR); Factors belonging to the students themselves (STT); Factors of learning conditions (LEC); Factors of university reputation (UNR); Factors of media activities (MEA); Factors of future job opportunities (JOO); and students' decision to choose a university (DEC).

Figure 1. Six factors influence students' decision to choose a university

2.3. Research hypothesis

On the basis of research theories, we propose a model of factors affecting the decision to choose a university for high school students in Vietnam. The following hypotheses have been proposed (H1): Factors affecting the decision to choose a university for high school students to include Factors consulted by teachers, family, friends, and relatives; Factors belonging to the students themselves; Factors of learning conditions; Factors of university reputation; Factors of media activities; Factors of future job opportunities.

According to Chapman, in choosing a university, students are strongly influenced by the persuasion of friends, family, and teachers [19]. The influence their advice has on students can go in many ways, including how their opinions influence expectations about a college; they can also advise directly on where students should take the test. In the case of a close friend, the place where the best friend takes the exam also affects the student's decision to choose a university [24], [25]. According to Hossler and Gallagher, family, close friends, and teachers are the factors that influence students' decisions [9]. Considering the educational conditions of Vietnam, the individual who has a great influence on a student's decision to choose a school is the student's teacher. Based on this group of influential individuals, the hypothesis (COR) is stated as (H1.1): The advice of families, teachers, friends, and relatives for students to take the entrance exam to a university. It has an influence on the student's decision to choose a university.

Chapman stated that the factors of individual students are one of the groups of factors that greatly influence their decision to choose a university. Among those factors, the student's own ability and interests are the two factors that affect the decision to choose a university [19]. Anam conducted a survey of influencing factors in the university selection process, they concluded that the broad and varied characteristics of the characteristics affect university choice [4]. This is consistent with the theory of behavior that leads students to decide to choose a university [26]. Most studies suggest that students will tend to choose a university that matches their economic conditions, personality, interests, and personal abilities. Therefore, the hypothesis (SST) is put forward as (H1.2): The ability and interest factors of high school students affect the decision to choose majors and universities.

Characteristics of learning conditions include university facilities, learning facilities, libraries, dormitories, diversity of subjects, location of learning facilities, extracurriculars, policy regime, and financial support. Currently, before choosing a university, high school students tend to research the university thoroughly. They are interested in what area the university is located in, and what major the school specializes in. If students choose a university, what is the accommodation like, is the dormitory clean, beautiful, and safe, and the learning environment like. A university located in a favorable location has many attractive fields of study; there are many academic competitions and extracurricular activities for students to participate in; the dormitory is clean and beautiful and has many places for students, which will attract many students to choose. This has been tested in the study [19], [27]. Therefore, the author proposes the research hypothesis as (H1.3): Academic conditions have an influence on students' decision to choose a university.

According to Chapman, the fixed factors of the university such as tuition fee, geographical location, cost support policy or dormitory environment will have an influence on the decision to choose a university [19]. Nguyen et al. added a number of university characteristics that influence students' decision to choose a university [28]. More specifically, factors such as scholarships, safety in dormitory conditions, the quality of students at the school, the popularity and reputation of the school, the admission rate, the school's benchmarks, and the school's academic standards. The attractiveness of the field of study will be the factor affecting students' decision to choose a school.

According to Joseph, a university's reputation can be understood in different ways. For example, university reputation is the prestige, the reputation of the school lingers in the minds of learners and the community when we talk about universities [29]. For a university, reputation is for the quality of education that students can perceive. The quality of education is reflected in the quality of the training program and the quality of the teaching staff. Research shows that university reputation is a very important factor affecting the choice of the university for high school students. Based on the group of factors about the characteristics of the university, the hypothesis (UNR) is stated as (H1.4): The better the university's reputation, the higher the tendency of high school students to choose a university.

Media is the transmission of information, ideas, attitudes, or feelings. Regarding the influence, the university's media activities are attractive [30], which will positively influence the student's decision to choose a university. This has been tested in the study [27], [31]. From that, the author makes the hypothesis (H1.5): Media activities have an influence on the decision of high school students to choose a university. That is, the university with more media activities, the higher the decision to choose a university for high school students.

Besides academic expectations in the future, future job expectations are also one of the factors affecting students' decision to choose a school [21]. Huong also suggested that personal readiness for work and chances of getting a job after graduation are also factors affecting students' decision to choose a school [32]. From the previous factors, the hypothesis (JOO) is stated as (H1.6): Employment rate or employment opportunities of students after graduating from a university has an influence on the decision to choose a university for high school students; (H2): Students between male and female groups, Students between grades, Students between high schools have different university choice decisions.

2.4. Data analysis

The answers from the survey were coded and entered into SPSS Version 20. The analysis and assessment of factors affecting the decision to choose a university for high school students are done through several steps. Step 1: Check the reliability of the scale through Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient. Step 2: exploratory factor analysis (EFA) to test the factors. Step 3: Using a linear regression model to determine factors affecting the decision to choose a university for high school students. Step 4: independent sample T-test analysis to test for mean gender differences, One-way ANOVA analysis to test mean differences between grades, and high schools.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Check the reliability of the scales

Testing the reliability of the factor scale consisting of 31 observed variables. The results of the Cronbach's Alpha reliability test of the scales show that six factors meet the requirements of reliability. Specifically, the factors consulted by teachers, family, friends, relatives (COR) scale has Cronbach's Alpha of 0.912; the factors belonging to the students themselves (STT) scale has Cronbach's Alpha of 0.855; the factors of learning conditions (LEC) scale has Cronbach's Alpha of 0.853; factors of university reputation (UNR) scale has Cronbach's Alpha of 0.930; the factors of media activities (MEA) scale has Cronbach's Alpha of 0.856; the factors of future job opportunities (JOO) scale has Cronbach's Alpha of 0.916. All six factors have Cronbach's Alpha coefficient > 0.6, so the scale is qualified as presented in Table 2. In addition, the total correlation coefficients of these scales are all higher than the allowed level (Corrected item-total correlation > 0.3), so all six scales are included in the exploratory factor analysis (EFA) [33].

Table 2. Reliability of the Cronbach Alpha scale

Factors	Observed variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Corrected item-Total correlation
COR	COR1, COR2, COR3, COR4, COR5, COR6	.912	> 0.3
STT	STT1, STT2, STT3, STT4, STT5, STT6	.855	> 0.3
LEC	LEC1, LEC2, LEC3, LEC4, LEC5	.853	> 0.3
UNR	UNR1, UNR2, UNR3, UNR4	.930	> 0.3
MEA	MEA1, MEA2, MEA3, MEA4, MEA5	.856	> 0.3
JOO	JOO1, JOO2, JOO3, JOO4, JOO5	.916	> 0.3

3.2. Exploratory factor analysis

After checking the reliability of the scale, EFA was performed to determine the correlation between the factors and the loading coefficient of Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO)=0.845 (satisfies $0.55 \leq KMO \leq 1$), Sig. Barlett's Test=0.000 (<0.05) [34]. Table 3 shows a good correlation between the observed variables. Results of exploratory factor analysis, six factors with Eigenvalue=2.142 (>1) were drawn from 31 observed

variables and Cumulative=68.414%. Table 4 shows that the 31 observable variables loaded on six factors and there were changes to the position of the variables. Thus, the EFA outputs generate a set of six factors and 31 observed variables as shown in Table 5. It can fit the data and model.

Table 3. KMO and Bartlett's test

KMO measure of sampling adequacy	Bartlett's test of sphericity		
	Approx. Chi-square	df	Sig.
.845	8021.625	465	.000

Table 4. Rotated component matrix

	Component					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
UNR5	.918					
UNR4	.913					
UNR6	.895					
UNR3	.819					
UNR2	.764					
UNR1	.743					
COR5		.872				
COR6		.847				
COR3		.801				
COR4		.796				
COR1		.746				
COR2		.727				
JOO4			.901			
JOO5			.891			
JOO3			.878			
JOO2			.817			
JOO1			.816			
STT6				.879		
STT4				.789		
STT5				.780		
STT1				.690		
STT2				.678		
STT3				.662		
MEA5					.868	
MEA4					.832	
MEA1					.794	
MEA2					.739	
MEA3					.652	
LEC5						.835
LEC3						.770
LEC2						.752
LEC1						.745
LEC4						.700

Table 5. Linear regression model

Factors	Observed variables	Variable types
COR	COR1, COR2, COR3, COR4, COR5, COR6	Independent
JOO	JOO1, JOO2, JOO3, JOO4, JOO5	Independent
UNR	UNR1, UNR2, UNR3, UNR4	Independent
MEA	MEA1, MEA2, MEA3, MEA4, MEA5	Independent
LEC	LEC1, LEC2, LEC3, LEC4, LEC5	Independent
STT	STT1, STT2, STT3, STT4, STT5, STT6	Independent
DEC	DEC1, DEC2, DEC3, DEC4	Dependent

3.3. Results analysis linear regression

When independent and dependent variables could be identified, a multiple regression model was used to determine the overall fit of the model and the relative contribution of each predictor to the total variance. The model summary is seen in Table 6. R^2 (Adjusted R square)=0.506 showed that the independent variables JOO, STT, MEA, UNR, COR, LEC explained 50.8% of the variation in the dependent variable PER. Check whether the overall regression model fits the data. This shows that the independent variables predict statistically significant for the dependent variable, Sig.=0.000 (<0.05) compared to the 5% significance level, so setting up the regression model is appropriate as presented in Table 7.

Table 6. Model summary

Model	R	R square	Adjusted R square	Std. Error of the estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.717	.514	.506	.61231	1.878

Table 7. ANOVA

Model	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Regression	152.859	6	25.476	67.951	.000
Residual	144.721	386	.375		
Total	297.580	392			

The correlation coefficient and variance were then tested to measure the effect of collinearity among the variables in the regression model as shown in Table 8. As shown in Table 8, the collinearity statistics (VIF) of all six independent variables is lower than 10, indicating that there is no autocorrelation, or multicollinearity in the model. There are six observable variables COR, STT, LEC, UNR, MEA, JOO have statistical significance (Sig.<0.05) and Standardized Coefficients Beta>0, demonstrating a positive influence on the dependent variable. From Table 8, the new model for the data is (1):

$$DEC = 0.343 * COR + 0.244 * JOO + 0.195 * MEA + 0.191 * LEC + 0.146 * UNR + 0.127 * STT \quad (1)$$

According to the linear regression results, there are six factors that affect the decision to choose a university for high school students, including factors consulted by teachers, family, friends, relatives; Factors of future job opportunities; Factors of media activities; Factors of learning conditions; Factors of university reputation; Factors belonging to the students themselves.

Table 8. Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	-1.500	.296		-5.065	.000		
COR	.396	.047	.343	8.457	.000	.765	1.307
STT	.176	.052	.127	3.377	.001	.884	1.131
LEC	.270	.056	.191	4.807	.000	.797	1.255
UNR	.180	.048	.146	3.771	.000	.844	1.185
MEA	.254	.049	.195	5.160	.000	.883	1.132
JOO	.283	.042	.244	6.711	.000	.954	1.048

3.4. Analysis of differences in university choice decisions for gender, grade, the high school

3.4.1. Analysis of differences between male and female groups on university choice decisions

Table 9 shows the analysis of the independent samples test has Sig.=0.51 (>0.05). This means that the variances of both the male and female groups are equal. Table 9 also shows that there is no significant mean difference between groups of males and groups of females (Sig. (2-tailed) =0.140 (>0.05). That is, the decision to choose a university for the male group and the female group is the same.

Table 9. Independent samples test

	Levene's test for equality of variances			t-test for equality of means						
	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean difference	Std. Error difference	95% confidence interval of the difference		
								Lower	Upper	
DEC	Equal variances assumed	3.836	.051	-1.490	391	.137	-.13085	.08785	-.30356	.04186
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.480	370.242	.140	-.13085	.08842	-.30473	.04303

3.4.2. Analysis One-way ANOVA of the decision to choose a university for high school students in the grades group

Table 10 shows Sig.=0.51 (>0.05). This means that the variance in the grades group on the decision to choose a university for high school students has no difference. When Table 10 has Sig.=0.51 (>0.05), ANOVA table will be used, research results showed Sig.=0.137 (>0.05). Thus, the decision to choose a university for high school students in the grades group has no difference.

Table 10. Checking the decision to choose a university for high school students in the grades group

Levene statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
3.836	1	391	.051

3.4.3. Analysis One-way ANOVA of the decision to choose a university for high school students in group the high school

Table 11 shows Sig.=0.108 (>0.05). This means that the variance in the group High School on the decision to choose a university for high school students has no difference of statistical significance. When Table 11 has Sig.=0.108 (>0.05), ANOVA table will be used, research results show Sig.=0.034 (<0.05). Thus, the decision to choose a university for high school students in group the High School has difference.

Table 11. Checking the decision to choose a university for high school students in group the high school

Levene statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
1.697	7	385	.108

3.5. Discussion

Initially, six factors were proposed to have influenced students' high school decision to choose a university. These were factors consulted by teachers, family, friends, and relatives (COR); factors belonging to the students themselves (STT); factors of learning conditions (LEC); factors of university reputation (UNR); factors of media activities (MEA); factors of future job opportunities (JOO). Statistical analyses employing EFA and linear regression models showed that all six factors significantly students' decision to choose a university. Multiple regression model as in (1) showed that the factor of consultation by teachers, family, friends, and relatives have the most influence on the decision to choose a university of high school students; followed by the factors of future job opportunities; factors of media activities; factors of learning conditions; factors of university reputation; factors belong to the students themselves.

Families should act as facilitators of student discovery and learning. Parents should spend a lot of time guiding students' careers; they should respect their children's perceptions and decisions. Parents are role models to help students understand the value of work and the fruits that are being enjoyed. Parents can tell their children about their profession [35]. Parents will help their children visualize more specifically and clearly. All of that will become lessons learned to teach students career orientation. Parents should accompany students when faced with decisive choices. They should be careful and skillful to analyze and help their children make a decision to choose the right university for themselves [36].

Employment and future job opportunities are factors that have a great influence on the decision to choose a university for high school students [37]. But when asked students what university and major they want to apply to? The answer received from students is that they want to apply to a university, which major they cannot be understated to answer [38]. Teachers and families also lack information about careers when high school students want to be consulted [39], [40]. The construction of complete information about the professions is intended to provide multi-dimensional information to students or to facilitate students to be consulted from many sources [41], [42]. This creates conditions for high school students to consult with friends, university students to advise them on majors, and students to listen to consultants explain majors [43], [44]. Students can refer to career information when needed from available means such as magazines, journals, and websites, it is good information for students to have a career choice suitable to their ability, his hobby [45].

Media activities are a factor affecting students' decision to choose a university. However, nowadays many students want to consult the information about majors at the universities they intend to choose, but the available information is only an admissions guide with brief information [46], [47]. Websites of universities are built up but hardly provide much information for students in high school to refer to [48], [49]. Therefore, universities want to attract more high school students to apply, so they should start building their own information supply system, more specifically, upgrading the website with the more necessary information for students in high school [50]. They should develop a magazine that introduces the professions the school offers, introduces scholarship opportunities, dormitory facilities, and cost assistance [51]. In addition, universities should announce graduation rates, and employment rates of students after graduation.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the theoretical model, the research has built and tested the reliability of the scale of factors affecting the decision to choose a university for high school students. The results of multiple linear regression analysis showed that the research model explained 50.6% of the overall relationship of the variables including: i) Factors consulted by teachers, family, friends, and relatives; ii) Factors belonging to the students themselves; iii) Factors of learning conditions; iv) Factors of university reputation; v) Factors of media activities; and vi) Factors of future job opportunities with high school student's decision to choose a university. The results show that factors consulted by teachers, family, friends, and relatives; factors of future job opportunities; factors of media activities; factors of learning conditions; factors of university reputation; factors belonging to the students themselves have affected the decision to choose a university of high school students. In which the factor of consultation with teachers, family, friends, and relatives has the greatest impact on the decision to choose a university for high school students.

The results of the T-test show that there is no difference between the groups of students by gender, and grade in high schools in the assessment of the importance of factors when deciding to choose a university. In addition, when analyzing ANOVA, the findings show that between groups of high schools there is a statistically significant difference in the decision to choose a university. The limitation of the study belongs to the research sample selected by the conventional method, the collected data may be partially influenced by the sample not carrying general significance. The implementation of research with a larger general sample is an open direction for further studies in the field of educational research.

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